

ISic3633

I.Sicily inscription 3633

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136011

1. [- - - ἐ]μὶ τῷ [] λιχίνα [---]

Edition: PHI336045

1. [τοῦ δεῖνα ἐ] | μὶ τῷ Διχίνα, ἡὸ [ς | ἀπέθανε(?) — —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645704

EDR 136011

PHI 336045

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 2000.0772

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